

D5.1 - Adaptations and recommendations report for future space exploration missions

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WP5.1– Adaptations towards Future Space Exploration Missions

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and Objectives

The LUXWEX (Lunar Water Extraction) project aims to develop and demonstrate technologies for the extraction and processing of water on the lunar surface. This document, Deliverable D5.1, details the design adaptations and recommendations derived from the project, focusing on both early demonstration missions and long-duration lunar surface missions.

1.2 Scope of the Document

This document, deliverable D5.1 for LUXWEX project, details LUXWEX design adaptations and recommendations for future space exploration missions including its technologies. It includes the technology designs and experiment results derived from WP 3 and WP 4, elaborated and integrated into an advanced design and recommendations for applications to both early demonstration as well as long-duration Lunar surface missions of the LUXWEX ISRU water process chain. These recommendations include mass, power and volume improvements as well as reliability, serviceability and compatibility with planned flight opportunities. The lessons learned with regard to system performance were established from laboratory testing results. A design study was performed to investigate the feasibility for a short-term demonstration of LUXWEX technologies on the Lunar surface (e.g. as part of a future mission of the European Large Logistics Lander).

1.3 Structure of the Document

The document is structured as follows:

1. Introduction
2. LUXWEX Design Adaptations
3. Technology Designs and Experiment Results
4. Recommendations for Future Space Exploration Missions
5. System Performance and Lessons Learned
6. Feasibility Study for Short-Term Demonstration
7. Conclusions

1.4 Applicable Documents

[AD1] LUXWEX-LSG-WP2.1-D2.1-System Requirements Document_v1.0

1.5 Reference Documents

- [RD1] D2.3-Preliminary Design Report
- [RD2] D3.1-Design definition and justification file
- [RD3] D3.2-Water extraction and liquefaction design report
- [RD4] D3.3-Water extraction and liquefaction hardware
- [RD5] D3.4-Water purification and storage design report
- [RD6] D3.5-Water purification and storage hardware
- [RD7] D3.6-Water quality and condition monitoring design report
- [RD8] D3.7-Quality and condition monitoring hardware
- [RD9] D3.8-LIBS technology for elemental analysis of water
- [RD10] D3.9-Assembly and integration report
- [RD11] D3.10-Assembled validation test stand
- [RD12] D4.1 Overall experiment report
- [RD13] D4.2 Lunar raw water simulant
- [RD14] D4.3 Lunar water ice simulant

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- [RD25] Purrington et al., Rapid Extraction of Volatiles from Excavated Icy Regolith Using a Rotary Extraction Drum, Earth and Space 2022
- [RD26] Colaprete, A. et al., 2010. Detection of Water in the LCROSS Ejecta Plume. *Science*, Volume 330, pp. 463-468. DOI: 10.1126/science.1186986
- [RD27] Janire Saez, Raquel Catalan-Carrio, Róisín M. Owens, Lourdes Basabe-Desmonts, Fernando Benito-Lopez, Microfluidics and materials for smart water monitoring: A review, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, Volume 1186, 2021

1.6 Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation
BBM	Breadboard Model
HW	Hardware
LIBS	Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy
MF	Microfiltration
PWR	Politechnika Wrocławska
RO	Reverse Osmosis
SWY	Scanway
TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia
TUBS	Technische Universität Braunschweig
TVAC	Thermal Vacuum chamber
WECS	Water Extraction and Capturing subsystem
WPS	Water Purification and Storage subsystem
WUST	Wroclaw University of Science and Technology

2 LUWEX Design Adaptations

2.1 Overview of LUWEX Technologies Design Status

The LUWEX ground demo experimental setup consists of the following subsystems:

- Data Acquisition, Control and Power
- Water Extraction and Capturing
- Water Purification and Storage
- Water Quality and Condition Monitoring
- Laboratory and Experiment Infrastructure (which includes the thermal vacuum chamber (TVAC))

and the following additional components:

- Ice-Regolith Simulant
- Raw Water Simulant

The TVAC is sealed and brought to the operative temperature and pressure. Ice regolith simulant is placed within the Water Extraction Subsystem (which is within the TVAC), which is then heated to achieve water ice sublimation. The water vapour is then frozen within the Water Capturing Subsystem onto a cold trap. The cold trap is then heated to allow solid water to enter the liquefaction compartment within the Water Capturing subsystem. In that position water is heated to reach the liquid phase (with part of it being on the vapour phase). Liquid water is transferred to the external storage reservoir (Storage I). The process is repeated up to when enough raw water is collected in storage I, then the water is transferred with a pump to Storage II reservoir. From there, water is processed within the Water Purification Subsystem in batch mode, with the product water collected in Storage III. Product water is then analysed in the Water Quality Monitoring Subsystem by flowing it through it from Storage III reservoir.

Figure 2-1 shows a block diagram of the overall system indicating a simplified version of the interfaces between the different subsystems and components.

Figure 2-1: Block diagram of the overall system of the LUWEX experimental setup. Dashed arrows indicate signal and power interfaces. Solid arrows indicate water (solid, liquid or gaseous state) flow

The current LUWEX ground demonstrator configuration allowed reaching TRL 4 at system level, as summarised in Figure 2-2. In order to further advance the system TRL, we need to consider that the above described subsystems and core elements are in part needed to simulate the LUWEX flight system operative environment on the Moon.

Figure 2-2: LUWEX system TRL evolution during current project phase

In order to focus on advancing the TRL of the system, the advancement of **following core technologies will we explored within this document:**

- Water Extraction and Capturing
- Water Purification and Storage
- Water Quality and Condition Monitoring

These technologies current design status is summarised in the following subsection, with reference to WP 3 project deliverables. Whenever testing activities related to WP 4 have impacted the WP 3 described design, such impacts have been assessed.

2.1.1 Water Extraction and Capturing current design status

2.1.1.1 Design status summary (from WP3)

In this section, a summary of the water extraction and liquefaction design report [RD3] is presented. Effectively, the design can be split into two distinct sections, the extraction subsystem, and the capturing subsystem, which consists of the capturing mechanism and the liquefaction chamber. Both these subsystems their designs are the result of a deep design investigation using trade-off tables and simulations. In Figure 2-3, a schematic overview of the entire WECS system is depicted, as well as the boundaries of the vacuum chamber in which it is placed, and the tube used for filling the crucible with the icy regolith simulant. Figure 2-4 shows how the assembled WECS system looks inside the TVAC.

Extraction subsystem:

Essentially, the main function of the extraction subsystem is to sublimate the ice that is in the icy regolith simulant to create water vapour and allow the water vapour to flow towards the capturing subsystem. A large issue with lunar regolith is its extremely low thermal conductivity, meaning that it will take a lot of time and energy for the ice to reach a temperature where it could sublimate. To improve the way heat disperses in the regolith by the heaters, we decided to implement a stirring mechanism that continuously stirs the regolith around by having the heating rods rotate around. The heating rods are all mounted at a different

radius from the centre, which ensures that there are no empty paths created in the icy regolith simulant. The stirring also makes it easier for the generated water vapour to outgas the dried-out parts of the regolith simulant.

Capturing subsystem:

The capturing subsystem is the cold trap and the liquefaction chamber. The cold trap its function is to let the water vapour deposit on it, by being a cold enough surface for deposition to happen. Once enough ice has deposited on the cold trap, heaters inside the cold trap will activate, and cause the connecting layer of ice to once again sublime, dropping the ice into the liquefaction chamber. The liquefaction chamber is then sealed off from the rest of the systems by a slider. Heaters inside the liquefaction chamber then cause the ice in there to melt, and this liquid water then flows into the storage I, that is outside of the TVAC. From Storage I, it can be transported to the purification system.

Figure 2-3: Schematic overview of the WECS inside and partially outside the TVAC. The parts inside the green dashed line are the extraction subsystem, and the components encircled by the blue dashed line are the capturing subsystem.

Figure 2-4: Photos of the assembled WECS inside the TVAC.

2.1.1.2 Design advancements after testing activities (WP4)

After the first attempt at a full water extraction and capturing experiment [RD12], it was noted that more dust than initially expected was travelling throughout the entire system. Especially the smallest particles present in the simulant were afterwards seen to cover almost every surface. The most critical issue this caused was that the slider was no longer sealing the liquefaction chamber from the rest of the system. With the slider not being able to seal the liquefaction chamber, the entire process of liquefying the water becomes much less optimal. Essentially, the extraction and capturing process must stop during liquefaction. It can be expected that with real lunar dust this scenario will not be very different. In the scenario described in section 2.2 Design Evolution and Adaptions, the capturing and liquefaction steps are already separated, so there will be no design consequence related to this example. However, for a smaller demonstration mission, there are lessons learned.

After the first tests with the fully assembled WECS, no design advancements have occurred. The operational concept has been slightly altered to ensure the captured water is liquefied, even if the slider does not completely seal. This has some implications in the time duration of the extraction, capturing and liquefaction as described in deliverable D4.1.

2.1.2 Water Purification and Storage current design status

2.1.2.1 Design status summary (from WP3)

LUXWEX Water Purification and Storage subsystem (WPS) treats water coming from Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem. Contaminated water extracted from Lunar surface is purified in the WPS to meet electrolysis feed water requirements.

The selection of contaminants and their concentration in tested water is based on literature [RD26] and on safety reasons project choices [RD14].

Techniques used for water purification

The choice of the technologies selected for the removal of contaminants was driven by the requirements of consuming less than 1g of consumables per kg of product water and of achieving target product water to feed ratio >95%, maximizing system reliability and maintainability. The selected technologies are also chosen for their scalability, from demonstration on a lunar lander to a final productive scenario. Contaminants to be

removed were divided into three categories: particulate, organics and inorganics. For each category the major removal technologies used are briefly described in the following section.

Design and operational principles

The water purification technologies used in LUXWEX WPS are listed below. A microfiltration membrane is used to remove particulate bigger than 0.45µm, expected in the form of lunar dust particles. Smaller dust particles are expected to not reach the WPS. The approach is considered conservative, since it is in general not clear whether and in which quantity these particles will actually reach the WPS. Indeed, the lunar dust dynamics within the previous WECS is not yet known.

For organics removal activated carbons (AC) are used. The concentration of organics contaminants is low so the associated consumables mass is limited. However, the option of regenerating AC using steam generated by product water to reduce subsystem consumables was considered. The AC are challenged by methanol as a critical contaminant that is still expected in the feed flow, although it should be mostly removed by the WECS when still in the gas phase. In the case that the LUXWEX system test will highlight that the quantity of methanol to be expected is higher than the current assumptions, further methods for TOC reduction will be implemented and are currently being studied.

Reverse osmosis (RO) as a first step for inorganics removal is chosen because of the high removal efficiency of all the present species, especially for ammonia, without the use of consumables. The RO concentrate is recirculated, allowing minimal process waste water generation. This is possible given the low concentration of inorganic contaminants in the feed flow. Ion exchange resins are used as final polishing technology to achieve purity requirement for the required technical water.

Figure 2-5: WPS integrated in LUXWEX rack

2.1.2.2 Design advancements after testing activities (WP4)

Figure 2-6 and Figure 2-7 show the average value on the runs of monitored parameters for each type water at the outlet of WPS subsystem.

In Figure 2-6 it is visible that TOC, the total amount of organic carbon present in outlet water, reaches required level according to AD1 for W1, W2, W4, W5 and W6, which does not contain methanol inside.

Methanol, due to its affinity with water, is the most critical contaminant to remove. Indeed Figure 2-6 shows that W3, W7, W8, have higher TOC level. ISS potable water limit for TOC is 0,5 ppm, this means that WPS can purify water containing methanol up to potable water level.

Furthermore, NASA SWEGs (Spacecraft Water Exposure Guidelines) set methanol limit in potable water at 15 ppm, which is well above the quantity present in LUWEX product water.

Even if TOC level for water containing methanol is slightly above the value required from ASTM D1193 for high purity water type II, the quantity of TOC is considered acceptable. Further studies are being carried on to improve WPS TOC removal technology.

Electrolysers require water with low electrical conductivity to improve efficiency, reliability and longevity. All the tested waters have EC values < 1 µS/cm after WPS as it is shown in Figure 2-6 c.

In electrolysers pH may influence reaction kinetics, ion transport and overall performances. Most of electrolysers (e.g. those based on proton exchange membranes - PEM) work with neutral pH values (pH = 7), which is compliant with LUWEX product water (Figure 2-6 d.). Some types of electrolysers (e.g. those using Static Feed Electrolysis - SFE) work with alkaline water (pH = 13) and pH can easily be enhanced adding potassium hydroxide (KOH) to water.

Figure 2-6: a. Average TOC results for Ws without methanol, b. Average TOC result for Ws with methanol, c. Average EC results for all Ws, d. Average pH results for all Ws

Figure 2-7: TOC and EC removal efficiency %

Figure 2-7 shows TOC and EC removal efficiency calculated starting from the measurements of contaminants in inlet water.

No design iteration where needed based on the tested and achieved performance.

2.1.3 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring current design status

2.1.3.1 Design status summary (from WP3)

Figure 2-8 presents the system topography. System is designed for the in-line measurement of water flowing through it, using LIBS technology. It is powered from the 220V AC supply. Commands and data are exchanged with data acquisition system. The measurement is carried out upon trigger and later the test result (ON/ NOT OK) is being returned. Raw measurement data and test results are being sent to database used by Scanway operating team. It is possible for operating team to update the software and system configuration over the internet.

Figure 2-8: System context diagram.

Water flows into the system and out of the systems through fluidic connectors agreed with TAS and WUST. The measurement is to be performed within the *enclosed laser compartment*, so no laser light cannot exit to the space of the laboratory. *Measurement chamber* is an interface between laser, spectrometer and studied water. PC communicates with DLR *data acquisition system* and commands the operation of laser and spectrometer, as well as controls the *power distribution unit*. Laser status indicator lamp communicates the laser status, so everyone present in the lab knows whether it is armed and operating. Figure 2-9 presents detailed components of the SWY system.

Figure 2-9: Internal architecture and system context of Quality and Condition Monitoring 1 system.

WUST subsystem consists of two modules measuring water quality parameters which are to be placed in the two points (named as PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2) of overall system, as it presented in diagram on the Figure 2-1. The first module (between micro filtration and reverse osmosis purifying parts) works independently, whereas the second one (PWR SENSORS 2) is coupled with SWY LIBS module being the part WQCM second part. Figure 2-11 presents schematic arrangement of the components.

Figure 2-10: Schematic diagram of two WQCM module (PWR SENSORS 1 and PWR SENSORS 2)

Each of two PWR SENSORS module consist of three analog probes (current) connected with multi-channel analyser allowing to display the measured parameters in real-time operation as well extracting them to external USB drive and DAQC module (Figure 2-11). All three probes are mounted into plastic piping system using threaded connection and bypassing the main line. The probes may be replaced, rearranged without any special tool nor extensive interference with module or subsystem architecture. The real-time measurement does not require special cell and does not affect water flow.

Figure 2-11: Three-sensor system

2.1.3.b Design advancements after testing activities (WP4)

The only upgrade made according to WUST subsystem (PWR SENSORS) was the piping architecture. As dedicated probe supports were utilized, allowing to smooth probe replacement, it was decided to drop the bypass conception (Figure 2-11, two T-shaped connectors and ¼” valves) and provide linear connection to the main piping system, not disturbing the flow of the liquid. Figure 2-12 presents CAD version of the final solution.

Figure 2-12: Single PWR SENSORS - overall view.

2.2 Design Evolution and Adaptations

The current LUWEX system design was driven by the needs of the ground demonstration, as introduced in section 2.1. We now need to evolve and adapt the design toward the LUWEX flight system, as a unit operative in the Moon environment.

In order to do so, it is mandatory to start **clarifying the operational scenario**. The current assumption (Figure 2-13) is that the LUWEX system is distributed within different elements of a lunar base infrastructure:

- The **Water Extraction and Capturing Subsystem (WECS)** is mounted onto a rover capable of driving to the permanently shadowed regions on the Moon, where the water ice contained within the Lunar regolith is harvested. Water ice is sublimated, then extracted water is frozen again and collected within the WECS. The collected frozen water is moved near the base, placed in the sun-lit region near the shadowed crater.
- Water is then liquefied at the sun-lit lunar infrastructure. Liquefaction is, as a first iteration, performed within the WECS when connected to the lunar base power system.
- Liquid “raw” water is then pumped to the **Water Purification Subsystem (WPS)**. The WPS removes contaminants to the desired water purity level. The WPS could either be housed into a dedicated facility in the sun-lit region, or within the Lunar Base. In the latter case, this would allow less stringent design requirements as well as proper maintenance (e.g. replacement of consumable items, cleaning).
- Product water is then analysed with the **Water Quality and Condition Monitoring Subsystem (WQMS)**. The WQMS assures product water quality with respect to applicable standards and it is placed in the same facility of the WPS.

Figure 2-13: LUWEX flight system preliminary operational scenario within Lunar base infrastructure

The following subsections describe the needed design evolution of the three core subsystems, in order to evolve and adapt the design toward the LUWEX flight system (described above).

2.2.1 Water Extraction and Capturing necessary design evolution

In the scenario described in the previous section, the capturing and liquefaction are done in separate locations, to make optimal use of the native environment of the Permanently Shadowed Regions (PSRs) on the Moon (i.e. cold crater in the PSR and sunlit crater edge). This means that the captured water is stored as ice until the extraction phase of the mission is over. In the current LUXEX design, intermediate liquefaction was foreseen, but due to dust issues with the slider that separates capturing and liquefaction, this was not possible. Additionally, ice delamination proved challenging due to the limited amount of power that could be delivered to the cold fingers, leading to slow delamination and some loss of captured material.

A better solution could focus on enhancing the cooling capability of the cold trap, leveraging the cold lunar environment. The cold trap would need to capture ice from multiple extraction attempts, and only once the cold trap is full, the rover would leave the PSR to passively liquefy the ice in sunlight. This approach shifts the system complexity towards the cold trap's surface area and cooling capacity but simplifies the overall design.

2.2.1.1 Functional Addition: Excavation or Drilling

Excavation or drilling was not included in our project because the chosen extraction method, a crucible, is agnostic toward the excavation system. It just needs to be supplied with icy regolith. The choice of the best excavation method depends on factors like the mission size, the location on the Moon, and how the ice is distributed in the regolith. Given the uncertainty of whether icy-regolith starts directly on the surface or is covered by a dry overburden (RD24), the optimal approach is uncertain. For the purpose of a technology demonstration, the most important goal is to show that ice can be reliably gathered, which implies that excavation or drilling is necessary.

2.2.1.2 Functional Change: Stirring and Emptying of Dry Regolith

In our experiments, the heaters were mounted on a stirring frame to speed up the extraction process. However, this would not be ideal with real lunar regolith, which is very abrasive and could damage the heaters. A rotating heated cylinder could be a better alternative (RD25). This design would spin and mix the regolith, whilst simultaneously heating the icy regolith allowing the ice to sublimate. This change would also require rethinking the filling and loading method to accommodate the new setup.

2.2.1.3 Functional Change: Capturing and Liquefaction Cycles

We observed that our design was highly susceptible to dust issues, particularly with components like sliders. To mitigate this risk, more robust valves or closing mechanisms may be necessary, or the design could be adjusted to remove the need for such components altogether. Another option is to resize parts of the system, such as the cold trap or liquefaction chamber, to prevent dust from interfering with other processes, as is described in the introduction of this section. Regardless, a reliable sealing surface will be required at some stage, and determining where this should be placed involves a trade-off that needs to be evaluated.

2.2.2 Water Purification and Storage necessary design evolution

The development of the Water Purification System (WPS) intended for use within a manned lunar base will need significant evolution from its initial laboratory breadboard design to the operative unit capable of long-term operation on the lunar surface. The breadboard version successfully demonstrated the purification of water in a controlled laboratory environment, providing a solid foundation for further design improvements. To ensure the system's reliability, maintainability, and functionality in the challenging lunar environment, several design considerations must be implemented. The evolution of the WPS includes the addition of steam regeneration for activated carbon (to reduce consumables usage), of a photocatalytic reactor for improved methanol removal, alongside crucial design enhancements in spare policy, redundancy, maintenance strategy, system configuration, crew accessibility, ergonomics, and system dormancy management. This chapter outlines these necessary design evolutions, focusing on their importance in ensuring the system's operability and longevity in a lunar base setting.

2.2.2.1 Functional Addition: Steam Regeneration of Activated Carbon

The primary functional evolution of the WPS involves adding steam regeneration for the activated carbon reactor. In the initial laboratory breadboard design, the activated carbon reactor provided efficient adsorp-

tion of organic contaminants but lacked a regeneration mechanism. For long-term lunar operations, the capability to regenerate the activated carbon using steam is critical for minimizing material resupply requirements and maximizing operational continuity.

The steam regeneration process involves the following:

- Heating a minimum amount of product water to generate steam within a controlled chamber.
- Passing the steam through the saturated activated carbon bed to desorb organic contaminants.
- Condensing and filtering the extracted steam to remove contaminants before recycling it into the system.

The system must include an energy-efficient heat source capable of generating steam reliably in the lunar environment. Options such as electrical or resistive heating can be explored.

Since the WPS operates within a pressurized and thermally controlled environment, maintaining thermal stability during steam regeneration is vital to prevent energy losses.

The system needs also an efficient condensation mechanism for recycling water and minimizing losses, with a focus on ensuring the purity of the recycled water.

2.2.2.2 *Functional Addition: Photocatalytic Reactor for Improved Methanol Removal*

In addition to steam regeneration for the activated carbon reactor, a photocatalytic reactor will be introduced to address the challenge of removing methanol at low concentrations. Methanol, a common contaminant in closed-loop water systems, cannot be effectively adsorbed by activated carbon at trace levels. To enhance purification efficiency, a photocatalytic reactor will be incorporated. This reactor utilizes ultraviolet (UV) light and a photocatalyst, such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂), to break down methanol into harmless by-products like water and carbon dioxide through a series of oxidation reactions. The unit will be developed based on the following design aspects:

- **UV Light Source:** A reliable, long-lasting UV light source will be integrated to activate the photocatalyst. The reactor must be designed to operate effectively in the lunar base's controlled environment.
- **Photocatalyst Efficiency:** The choice of a durable, high-surface-area catalyst, such as nano-structured TiO₂, will maximize the degradation of methanol with minimal maintenance.
- **Byproduct Management:** The system will manage any byproducts of the photocatalytic process, ensuring that they do not interfere with the system's overall water quality or require additional purification steps.

This addition significantly enhances the WPS's capability to maintain high water purity, especially in removing methanol that the activated carbon reactor cannot efficiently handle at low concentrations.

2.2.2.3 *Spare Policy and Redundancy*

To ensure the WPS operates with minimal downtime and maximum reliability in a lunar base, a well-planned spare policy and system redundancy are essential and need to be studied further.

The WPS spare policy must be designed to address the challenges of space missions, including long resupply times and limited cargo capacity. Key strategies include:

- **Critical components inventory:** Stockpiling essential spare parts (e.g., filters, pumps, sensors) that have a high likelihood of failure.
- **Modular design:** Using a modular architecture for easily replaceable parts that allows for swapping components without significant disassembly.
- **Preventive replacement cycles:** Establishing a schedule for replacing wear-prone parts before failure occurs, extending system longevity.

System redundancy, on another note, is crucial to avoid single points of failure and maintain continuous water purification operations. The redundancies strategy needs to be defined based on the criticality of the

WPS for the lunar base architecture, which is not defined yet. Key systems, such as pumps, sensors, and filters, could have redundant counterparts running in parallel. In case of a failure, the backup system can be activated without compromising water purification.

2.2.2.4 Maintenance Strategy

Maintenance on the lunar surface requires careful planning to minimize crew intervention, maximize uptime, and ensure system reliability over long mission durations. The maintenance strategy should consider:

- **Scheduled maintenance tasks:** Regular maintenance intervals should be predefined based on the anticipated wear rates of components, taking into account lunar dust contamination risks and equipment wear.
- **Automated monitoring:** Integrated sensors can track the system's performance in real time, triggering alerts for required maintenance or component replacement.
- **Tool and spare accessibility:** Maintenance procedures should be designed with minimal tool requirements and easy access to critical components, reducing crew time spent on repairs.

2.2.2.5 Configuration Study and Crew Accessibility

The physical layout and configuration of the WPS must ensure that it integrates efficiently within the lunar base while allowing for easy access to the system for maintenance and operation.

The WPS must be configured to fit within the spatial constraints of the lunar habitat and accommodate the base's broader systems, such as power, water supply, and waste management. The following aspects should be considered:

- **Compactness and modularity:** The system should be compact to conserve space while remaining modular for ease of transport, installation, and maintenance.
- **Interfacing with the base's infrastructure:** The WPS should integrate seamlessly with the lunar base's piping, electrical systems, and control interfaces.
- **Physical accessibility:** The placement of key components such as pumps, filters, and the activated carbon reactor should ensure they are easily accessible for crew members during routine maintenance. Considerations for minimal bending, reaching, or lifting should be factored into the system design.
- **Visual indicators:** The system should feature clear visual status indicators, accessible control panels, and simplified interfaces for real-time monitoring and control by the crew.
- **Task simplification:** Maintenance tasks must be simplified as much as possible, with intuitive assembly and disassembly processes to reduce crew training time and workload.

2.2.2.6 Ergonomics

Ergonomics plays a vital role in ensuring that crew members can interact with the WPS safely and efficiently. The system's design must accommodate the lunar habitat's constraints while considering the physical capabilities and limitations of astronauts operating in lunar gravity.

- **Work surface height:** The system should be designed at an optimal height to minimize strain during maintenance and operation, avoiding the need for excessive bending or awkward postures.
- **Component weight:** Given the reduced gravity, components that require handling should be designed to ensure safe and easy manipulation by the crew, reducing the risk of injury.
- **Tool ergonomics:** Any tools needed for maintenance should be designed for easy use in the lunar environment, considering potential restrictions posed by space suits.

2.2.2.7 System Dormancy Strategy

Given that the lunar base may not operate continuously, the WPS must have a robust dormancy strategy to handle extended periods of inactivity without compromising performance or damaging the system.

During periods of non-use, the system should be capable of entering a dormant state that minimizes power consumption and prevents degradation of key components. This may involve:

- **Drying procedures:** Ensuring the system is free of water to avoid microbial growth or freezing during dormancy.
- **Component preservation:** Implementing methods to protect sensitive components, such as lubricating pumps or sealing filters to prevent exposure to lunar dust.

The system should feature easy and quick reactivation procedures, including automated system checks to ensure that all components are operational before resuming water purification tasks. This would involve automated leak detection, pressure testing, and flow verification before full operation is restored.

2.2.3 Water Quality and Condition Monitoring necessary design evolution

There are several aspects of the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring subsystem design that are crucial to improve in the context of future lunar mission. To name them:

- system mass, dimension and power reduction
- material selection
- radiation tolerance
- in mission calibration
- increase system reliability and safety

Assuming that the subsystem will be operated within a pressurised module in controlled atmosphere, the following lunar environment design constraints are not implemented by the subsystem design:

- Lunar surface temperature range tolerance
- Lunar surface vacuum tolerance
- Lunar dust tolerance

According to the WQCM, WUST part, pH, EC and Turbidity COTS sensors were selected for the breadboard. Sensible mass and envelope savings can be achieved by replacing standard sensors with much smaller and lighter sensors used in a microfluidics. The concept of shrink sensors used in laboratory applications has been described in scientific papers [RD27]. The disadvantage of described solution for the current project phase was related to cost-effectiveness aspects, but it would not be an issue for a space application. In more detail, the following modifications could be needed for each sensor type:

- **pH Sensor** switch to a solid-state sensor: Replace liquid-based pH probes (which may be prone to freezing or evaporation) with solid-state ion-sensitive field-effect transistor (ISFET) pH sensors. These are more durable and suitable for the vacuum and extreme temperatures.
- **Electrical Conductivity (EC) Sensor:** switch to non-contact sensors: Employ non-contact conductivity sensors to avoid issues related to electrode corrosion or fouling in the lunar environment.
- **Turbidity Sensor** sealed fluid container: since fluids behave differently in low gravity, house the water sample in a sealed container to avoid evaporation or abnormal particulate settling.

Regarding the WQCM, SCW part, a laser spectrometer was assembled from COTS components, but with a customized layout. The laser source is the bulkiest part of this system and designing much smaller laser system is crucial for the adaptation, as the laser is responsible for over 90% of the SCW WQCM hardware volume. Another issue is fragility of the measurement cell, which most probably would need to custom designed to not break down due to spaceflight vibrations. Finally, the system would need to be tested in reduced-gravity conditions before being launched to space, as differences in how fluid behaves could alter the final effect of laser on water (dynamics of water flow, behaviour of gas). Zero-g flight or drop tower campaign could be reasonable intermediate step for further understanding and evolution of this technology.

2.3 Integration with Existing Systems

The objective of this section is to analyse and outline the additional requirements and methods for integrating the LUXWEX system with other lunar mission components and infrastructure to ensure seamless operation and maximize synergies.

2.3.1 Interface Requirements

The LUXWEX system requires precise mechanical, electrical, and data interfaces to integrate seamlessly with lunar landers and rovers. Mechanical interfaces include standardized mounting points and structural supports designed to withstand the lunar environment. Electrical interfaces involve robust connectors for power supply, with voltage and current specifications matching the available sources on lunar missions. Data interfaces utilize established communication protocols to enable control and monitoring of the LUXWEX system from mission control and other lunar systems.

2.3.2 Power System Integration

LUXWEX modules will be powered primarily by solar panels or nuclear power units available on the lunar surface. The system includes a power management module to ensure efficient power usage, incorporating energy storage solutions like batteries to manage peak loads and provide continuous operation during lunar nights.

2.3.3 Thermal Management

Efficient thermal management is critical for LUXWEX operation. The system incorporates radiators and heat sinks to dissipate heat generated during operation. Thermal protection measures, such as insulation, ensure the system's functionality in the extreme temperature variations of the lunar environment.

2.3.4 Mobility and Deployment

LUXWEX modules designed for mobility can be mounted on lunar rovers, allowing access to shadowed regions with ice deposits. For stationary operations, LUXWEX can be deployed from lunar landers, with considerations for impact forces during landing and setup procedures for optimal operation.

2.3.5 Operational Synergies

The LUXWEX system complements other ISRU technologies, such as oxygen extraction units. By integrating water extraction and purification processes with these systems, resource utilization on the lunar surface could be optimized (e.g. the regolith can be already heated to a certain temperature and volatiles removed by the extraction step). Additionally, purified water from LUXWEX can be supplied directly to lunar habitats, supporting life support systems and other essential operations.

2.3.6 Compatibility with Planned Missions

LUXWEX development aligns with the timelines of upcoming lunar missions, including NASA's Artemis program and ESA's European Large Logistics Lander. Design adaptations ensure compliance with mission constraints such as mass, volume, and safety standards, facilitating smooth integration and deployment.

2.3.7 Testing and Validation

Extensive pre-launch integration tests will validate the LUXWEX system's compatibility with existing systems. Upon successful deployment, operational validation procedures will confirm system performance, ensuring reliable operation on the lunar surface.

3 Recommendations for Future Space Exploration Missions

3.1 Upcoming lunar missions review: a focus on water ice investigation

Coming missions to the Lunar surface and, particularly, the lunar south pole, aim to answer the open questions regarding water on the Moon. The development of lunar water mining technologies, as well as water capturing and extraction systems, requires filling the existent knowledge gaps such as its form, distribution and concentration. The Volatiles Investigation Polar Exploration Rover (VIPER) could investigate the form and location of volatiles at the lunar south pole [RD17]. However, the mission is currently suspended due to reductions in NASA's exploration budget. Among its instruments, the TRIDENT drill will excavate the subsurface material gathering information on the ice rich and dry regolith geomechanical vertical properties [RD18]. A layer of permafrost may be found on the lunar regolith, giving it a great resistance to be excavated. Hence, the findings of this experiment are crucial for future large-scale excavation activities and to understand the state of the icy mixture before extraction experiments. VIPER will also focus on finding other volatiles, using the spectrometer MSolo, focusing on the volatile released around the landing area and from drilling operations [RD16]. Such observations will have profound implications in the design of future water purification systems, once the volatiles and other contaminants that make their way to the lunar water are determined.

Lunar water distribution and lunar water cycle will be studied by NASA's mission Lunar Trailblazer, expected to launch in late 2024 [RD20]. Trailblazer will investigate the form of water in lunar sunlit areas and help decipher the water cycle. Knowing the distribution of water ice in sun lit regions is essential to quantify the amount of water that can be readily available for extraction, as well as its concentration. Trailblazer will also look into the PSRs at the lunar poles to determine the form and abundance of ice. The mission is designed so its instruments can discern between OH, H₂O and water ice, thanks to their high spectral resolution. Knowing the state of the ice in sunlit regions will help assess the feasibility of its mining and extraction, as well as tailor the design of the extraction systems. Figure 3-1 shows the current understanding of the lunar water cycle. Depending on the origin mechanism, different physical characteristics are expected that shape the possible system architecture. Particularly, the lack of direct visual evidences of frost or ice in small PSRs suggest that large concentrations of water ice might just be accessible under the surface [RD21]. Therefore, future payloads aiming to extract water ice may be required to have extraction capabilities or be supported by other excavation instruments/payloads. Furthermore, this investigation will be supported by further results coming from the findings of the Korea Pathfinder Lunar Orbiter, which released its first data set to the scientific community in June 2024 [RD22].

Chandrayaan-3 was the first lander to reach the lunar south pole and performed in-situ measurements [RD19]. Among the results of the mission, a higher concentration of sulfur than anticipated was found on the lunar regolith. Sulfur can have an important role in ISRU, as its uses range from fertilizer to water-less concrete production. However, it can also be a form of contamination if it finds its way to water, leading to health issues and corrosion. Depending on the distribution of sulfur and its amount, it may be specifically addressed during a purification process.

Figure 3-1: Lunar water cycle. Credit: Caltech

3.2 Early Demonstration Missions - Technology Demonstration Test Campaign

To design a technology demonstration test campaign for the LUWEX system using planned lunar landers and rovers, we should consider a phased approach (conceptually pictured in Figure 3-2).

Figure 3-2: Conceptual image of LUWEX phased approach for TRL advancement

This approach starts with process-specific demonstrators and progressively scales up to a full system demonstration, in order to achieve TRL 7, which is the recommended TRL level for actual deployment of an operative system (see Figure 3-3). This incremental strategy minimizes risk, gathers crucial data, and refines technologies before a comprehensive deployment. The strategy would benefit for short term planned lunar missions, including both lunar landers and rovers.

LUNAR FLIGHT OPPORTUNITIES

Institutional (EL3)
CLPS (e.g. Astrobotic, Intuitive Machines, i-Space)

Figure 3-3: Opportunities for LUWEX system advancement to TRL 7

A detailed outline for the TRL advancement test campaigns is reported as follows.

3.2.1 Phase 1: Process-Specific Demonstrators

3.2.1.1 1.1. Water Extraction from Regolith

Objective: Demonstrate the sublimation and capture of water from lunar regolith.

Key Activities:

- **Selection of Test Site:** Choose a permanently shadowed region with known ice deposits.
- **Payload Development:** Develop a small-scale water extraction unit capable of heating regolith to sublimate ice and capture water vapor on cold fingers.
- **Integration with Rover:** Integrate the unit with a lunar rover equipped with suitable power supply and mobility to access shadowed regions.
- **Testing and Data Collection:** Operate the unit to sublimate ice, capture water vapor, and measure the efficiency of the process. Collect data on energy consumption, extraction rate, and environmental effects.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Collaborate with missions like NASA's VIPER rover or commercial lunar payload services (CLPS) that target shadowed regions.

3.2.1.2 1.2. Water Liquefaction

Objective: Demonstrate the condensation and liquefaction of captured water vapor.

Key Activities:

- **Development of Liquefaction Module:** Create a module that condenses water vapor and collects it as liquid water. This module can be tested independently or integrated with the water extraction unit.
- **Thermal Management:** Implement a cooling system to ensure efficient condensation and minimize loss due to re-sublimation.
- **Data Collection:** Measure the efficiency of condensation, power consumption, and the quantity of liquid water collected.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Integrate with mid-sized lunar landers or habitat modules capable of providing the necessary power and thermal management infrastructure.

3.2.1.3 1.3. Water Purification

Objective: Demonstrate the purification of lunar-derived water to meet the standards for human consumption or use in life support systems.

Key Activities:

- **Development of Purification Unit:** Design a compact, robust water purification system using filtration, distillation, or other suitable methods.
- **Integration with Liquefaction Module:** Ensure compatibility with the liquefaction module to form a complete water processing chain.
- **Testing and Data Collection:** Validate the purity of the water through chemical analysis and measure the efficiency and power consumption of the purification process.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Utilize a stationary lunar habitat or research module to provide continuous power and facilitate extended testing.

3.2.2 Phase 2: Full System Demonstration

3.2.2.1 2.1. Integrated System Testing

Objective: Demonstrate the full LUXWEX system, integrating extraction, liquefaction, and purification units.

Key Activities:

- **System Integration:** Assemble all three modules (extraction, liquefaction, purification) into a cohesive system capable of autonomous operation.
- **Simulation and Pre-deployment Testing:** Conduct rigorous simulations and pre-deployment testing in lunar analog environments on Earth.
- **Rover and Lander Collaboration:** Integrate the full system with a capable lunar rover and/or lander, ensuring adequate power supply, thermal management, and data communication systems.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Coordinate with large-scale missions such as ESA's European Large Logistics Lander (EL3) or Artemis program missions which have the capacity to support and deploy complex systems.

3.2.2.2 2.2. Deployment and Operational Testing

Objective: Validate the performance of the LUXEX system in the lunar environment over an extended period.

Key Activities:

- **Landing and Setup:** Deploy the integrated LUXEX system to a selected lunar site with optimal ice deposits.
- **Operational Phase:** Run the system through multiple cycles of water extraction, liquefaction, and purification. Monitor system performance, reliability, and maintenance requirements.
- **Data Analysis:** Collect and analyze data to assess efficiency, energy consumption, water yield, and system resilience.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Partner with missions providing extended lunar surface operations, such as the Artemis Base Camp, to ensure continuous support and monitoring.

3.2.3 General Design Considerations for Lunar Demonstrators

Design considerations for early demonstration missions include:

- **Compactness:** The technology must be designed to fit within the payload constraints of current launch vehicles.
- **Energy Efficiency:** Systems must operate efficiently within the limited power available on early lunar missions.
- **Modularity:** Technologies should be modular to allow for incremental testing and scaling up in future missions.
- **Automation:** Given the limited human presence, systems should be highly automated with minimal need for manual intervention.

3.3 Long-Duration Lunar Surface Missions

Objective: Integrate the LUXEX system into long-term lunar bases for sustained water production.

Key Activities:

- **System Scalability:** Scale the LUXEX system to meet the needs of a permanent lunar base, addressing increased demand for water.
- **Infrastructure Integration:** Connect the LUXEX system with habitat life support systems, power grids, and other ISRU technologies.
- **Continuous Operation and Maintenance:** Establish protocols for continuous operation, routine maintenance, and system upgrades based on long-duration mission requirements.

Planned Mission Collaboration: Collaborate with international lunar base initiatives, leveraging infrastructure and logistical support for long-term deployment.

3.3.1 Mass, Power, and Volume Improvements

For long-duration missions, it is crucial to optimize mass, power, and volume. Recommendations include:

- **Lightweight Materials:** Utilize advanced, lightweight materials to reduce the overall mass of the equipment.
- **Energy-efficient Processes:** Implement energy-saving measures and efficient power management to ensure sustainable operations.
- **Compact Design:** Design systems to be as compact as possible without compromising functionality, to maximize the use of available space.

3.3.2 Reliability and Serviceability

Reliability and serviceability are paramount for long-term missions:

- **Robust Design:** Ensure all components are designed to withstand the harsh lunar environment, including extreme temperatures and radiation.
- **Redundancy:** Incorporate redundant systems to mitigate the risk of failures.
- **Ease of Maintenance:** Design systems for easy maintenance and repair, with accessible components and clear procedures.

3.3.3 Compatibility with Planned Flight Opportunities

To ensure compatibility with future lunar missions, LUXEX technologies should align with planned flight opportunities:

- **Standard Interfaces:** Use standardized interfaces to facilitate integration with various lunar landers and habitats.
- **Mission Planning:** Coordinate with space agencies and commercial partners to align technology development with upcoming missions.
- **Scalability:** Ensure that technologies can be scaled to meet the needs of different mission profiles, from small robotic missions to large crewed missions.

4 Feasibility Assessment for Short-Term Demonstration

4.1 Assessment of the complete process chain

For an early technology demonstration with a lunar lander we considered the following options, as single process demonstrators:

1. Water extraction from regolith
2. Extracted water Liquefaction
3. Extracted water Purification

Table 4-2 reports a detailed comparison among the three considered subsystems, with the objective of identifying one favourite subsystem for an early demonstration mission. The following criteria are used:

- Scientific Value and Mission Relevance
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
- Compatibility with Lunar Lander Constraints
- Early Mission Alignment
- Standalone Feasibility

Based on the five assessment criteria (summarised in Table 4-1), **water extraction** remains the most likely subsystem to be demonstrated early on lunar missions. However, **water liquefaction** and **purification** subsystems would play critical roles in the later stages of lunar exploration as ISRU systems evolve toward supporting long-term human missions.

Table 4-1: Comparative Summary of Subsystem Feasibility

Criteria	Water Extraction	Water Liquefaction	Water Purification
Scientific Value and Mission Relevance	High: Critical for ISRU validation, first step in water use	Medium-High: Converts vapor to liquid, essential for usable water	Medium-High: Ensures clean water for human use, critical for habitats
Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	Medium-High (TRL 5-6): Adaptation required for lunar conditions	Medium (TRL 4-5): Needs adaptation for vacuum and cooling	Medium (TRL 5-6): Mature, needs adaptation for lunar contaminants
Compatibility with Lander Constraints	High: Moderate mass/volume, manageable power needs	Medium: More hardware (radiators, compressors), higher power needs	Medium: Low to moderate power, compact but requires liquid water
Early Mission Alignment	High: Ideal for early ISRU demonstration	Medium: Important, but secondary to extraction	Medium-Low: Relevant for long-duration missions, less for early demos
Standalone Feasibility	High: Can operate independently as a demonstrator	Low-Medium: Relies on prior water extraction	Low: Depends on extraction and liquefaction

Thus, **water liquefaction** would likely be the next logical step after water extraction, especially as missions evolve to more advanced ISRU demonstrations, and it is further detailed in the following section. **Water purification** would follow as human habitation becomes a focal point, requiring clean, usable water for life support and other uses. However, both systems are unlikely to be demonstrated independently in the very early missions.

Table 4-2: Comparison of LUXWEX single process lunar surface early demonstrators

Parameter	Water extraction from regolith	Extracted water Liquefaction	Extracted water Purification
Scientific Value and Mission Relevance	<p>High Value: The extraction of water from lunar ice deposits is critical for future lunar missions because it directly addresses the need for in-situ resource utilization (ISRU). Demonstrating extraction would be a milestone, confirming that water can be harvested from the Moon's surface. This process is foundational for producing water for human consumption, agriculture, and fuel.</p> <p>Mission Relevance: It has high relevance to early lunar missions, particularly those investigating the Moon's resources in permanently shadowed regions.</p>	<p>Medium to High Value: Liquefaction has significant scientific value as it converts water vapor (extracted from lunar ice) into liquid water, which is directly usable for life support, construction, and fuel production. Demonstrating liquefaction is critical for developing a full in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) water process chain.</p> <p>Mission Relevance: Liquefying water on the lunar surface would be a key step towards establishing sustainable lunar habitats or bases. However, it is secondary to water extraction itself, since extraction is the first step in confirming the availability of water on the Moon.</p>	<p>Medium to High Value: Purification is essential for ensuring that extracted and liquefied water is safe and usable for life support systems. Demonstrating this on the Moon would be a key step toward establishing a closed-loop system where lunar resources (water) can directly support human life and operations.</p> <p>Mission Relevance: The purification system is less relevant in the early stages of lunar exploration but becomes crucial as ISRU systems evolve to support long-duration missions. In missions focused on sustainability and the production of consumable resources, purification plays a critical role.</p>
Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	<p>Medium to High (TRL 5-6): Heating and sublimation processes are well understood from terrestrial applications, and laboratory prototypes have been tested using lunar simulants. However, the subsystem still needs to be adapted to the extreme lunar conditions (low gravity, low pressure, and extreme cold).</p>	<p>Medium (TRL 4-5): Water liquefaction processes are well understood and have been used in many industrial and laboratory applications on Earth. However, demonstrating liquefaction in the lunar environment introduces new challenges, especially with regard to the extreme temperature differences on the Moon, making it a lower TRL compared to water extraction from regolith.</p> <p>Environmental Challenges: Thermal management is the main concern. The extreme cold in permanently shadowed lunar regions complicates condensation and requires robust cooling and thermal control systems.</p>	<p>Medium (TRL 5-6): Water purification technologies, such as filtration, distillation, or chemical treatment, are mature and widely used on Earth, including in space missions (e.g., on the International Space Station). However, adapting them to the lunar environment, where water may contain lunar dust and volatile contaminants, introduces new challenges. Dust mitigation and lunar-specific contaminants may require further testing and optimization, especially with a new water source like lunar ice.</p>

Parameter	Water extraction from regolith	Extracted water Liquefaction	Extracted water Purification
<p>Compatibility with Lunar Lander Constraints</p>	<p>High Compatibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass and Volume: Water extraction systems are relatively compact and can be designed to fit within the constraints of a mid-sized lunar lander. The primary hardware components, such as heating elements and cold fingers for capturing water vapor, have moderate size and weight. • Power Requirements: Moderate power (50-100 W) is needed to heat the regolith and operate the cold finger mechanism, which should be manageable for most lunar landers. 	<p>Medium Compatibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass and Volume: The liquefaction system adds additional hardware (e.g., radiators, compressors, cooling loops) which increases the payload mass and volume. The lander must allocate additional space and power to accommodate these systems, which may be a challenge on small or early landers. • Power Requirements: Liquefaction processes typically consume not negligible power. Cooling systems or compressors needed to condense water vapor into liquid would require sustained power over long periods, which may exceed the available power budget of early lunar landers relying on solar panels. 	<p>Medium Compatibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mass and Volume: Purification systems are relatively compact and lightweight, consisting of filters, chemical treatment units, or small distillation systems. Therefore, they could fit within the payload constraints of many lunar landers. • Power Requirements: Purification systems can be relatively low-power, especially in cases where filtration or chemical treatment is used instead of distillation or advanced systems. However, more complex purification methods (e.g., reverse osmosis) might require more power and cooling infrastructure.
<p>Early Mission Alignment</p>	<p>High Relevance: Water extraction aligns with the goals of early lunar missions, particularly those focused on resource validation and ISRU demonstration. Proving that water can be extracted from regolith would provide key data for future missions aiming to establish sustainable human presence.</p> <p>Priority for Demonstration: High, as it addresses the first step in using lunar resources for human exploration.</p>	<p>Medium Relevance: Early missions prioritize low-complexity, high-impact experiments, making it unlikely that liquefaction would be a first-tier demonstrator. Although important for full ISRU systems, it may not be an immediate priority unless paired with water extraction in a more comprehensive system.</p> <p>Target Missions: Missions targeting long-duration lunar exploration, such as NASA's Artemis Base Camp or ESA's</p>	<p>Medium-Low Relevance: Water purification is most relevant for long-term human presence on the Moon, where continuous access to clean water is necessary. In early technology demonstration missions, purification may be less of a priority unless combined with water extraction and liquefaction to show the entire water process chain. It is unlikely that a purification subsystem would be flown as a stand-alone demonstration.</p>

Parameter	Water extraction from regolith	Extracted water Liquefaction	Extracted water Purification
		<p>planned habitats, would eventually require water liquefaction technologies. However, it is likely to be a secondary or later-phase technology demonstration after successful water extraction.</p>	<p>Integration with Early Missions: It could be aligned with later Artemis or ESA missions that focus on supporting human habitation, but it might not be as relevant in the earliest demonstration missions targeting just extraction or ISRU validation.</p>
<p>Standalone Feasibility</p>	<p>High: Water extraction can be demonstrated as a standalone subsystem without requiring other ISRU components. This makes it an excellent candidate for early technology demonstration missions, especially since its results (extracted water vapor) could be verified without needing liquefaction or purification systems initially.</p>	<p>Low to Medium: Water liquefaction is dependent on water extraction. As a standalone subsystem, liquefaction does not make sense without prior water extraction unless it is combined with an external source of water vapor. This makes it less feasible for isolated demonstration. Integration Requirement: Liquefaction will be most useful when integrated into a larger ISRU system, where it follows the extraction process and can function as part of a larger demonstration.</p>	<p>Low to Medium: Like liquefaction, purification is dependent on a preceding subsystem—liquefaction. It does not make sense as a stand-alone demonstration without the presence of liquid water to purify. While it is technically feasible to purify water brought from Earth or obtained via extraction, its stand-alone demonstration value is limited unless part of a more comprehensive water process chain. Integration with Existing Systems: In later stages, purification can easily integrate with water liquefaction and extraction systems, but it would likely not be prioritized for early, small-scale demonstrations.</p>

4.2 Feasibility Study for a Demonstrator of Water Extraction from Lunar Regolith Subsystem

This feasibility study focuses on the deployment of a **water extraction from regolith subsystem** as part of a demonstrator on a planned European lunar lander mission. The goal is to demonstrate the extraction of water from lunar regolith using sublimation techniques, targeting areas with high concentrations of ice in permanently shadowed regions. Specifically, we aim to integrate this subsystem into **ESA's European Large Logistics Lander (EL3)** or a similar mission.

The study examines the technical, logistical, and operational considerations for achieving this goal, considering the specific constraints of a lunar lander mission.

4.2.1 Objectives

The primary objectives of the water extraction demonstrator are as follows:

- **Objective 1:** Demonstrate the ability to extract water from lunar regolith by heating ice-containing regolith and capturing water vapor.
- **Objective 2:** Validate the use of cold finger technology for capturing water vapor and assessing its efficiency in the lunar environment.
- **Objective 3:** Collect and analyze data on extraction rates, power consumption, and system performance to support further development of in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) technologies.
- **Objective 4:** Establish a baseline for future integrated ISRU systems, including water liquefaction and purification.

4.2.2 Technical Overview

The demonstrator will be based on the **sublimation and cold finger** approach, followed during the LUXEX breadboard test campaign, to extract water from lunar regolith containing ice. The key elements of the surface demonstrator include:

- **Drilling and Heating Unit:**
 - Allows heated finger/s to be inserted into the regolith and ice bulk
 - Heats the regolith to a temperature sufficient to sublimate the ice (around 150-200°C).
 - Utilizes resistive heaters or induction heating, powered by the lander's power supply or solar panels.
- **Cold Finger Assembly:**
 - Positioned above the heated regolith to capture sublimated water vapor.
 - Operates at a controlled low temperature range to cause water vapor to condense and freeze on its surface, while keeping other contaminants in the gas phase.
- **Water Collection Chamber:**
 - A small, insulated chamber where condensed water vapor (ice) accumulates on the cold finger surface.
 - Equipped with sensors to measure the amount of captured water and monitor the system's performance.
- **Thermal Insulation:**
 - Ensures that the heat applied to the regolith does not dissipate into the lunar environment or affect other subsystems.
- **Temperature and Pressure Sensors:**
 - Integrated to monitor system performance, including internal temperatures, pressure changes due to sublimation, and the energy used for heating.

The demonstrator will benefit from landing near a permanently shadowed region where lunar ice is likely present, maximizing the chances of success for water extraction. Upon landing, the EL3 lander could deploy a robotic arm or other mechanism to position the extraction unit directly into the regolith. This may involve

using a small drill or auger to ensure sufficient regolith exposure to ice layers. The water extraction unit will operate autonomously once deployed. The lander or mission control on Earth will monitor system performance through data telemetry.

The following table outlines the target resource requirements for the water extraction demonstrator.

Table 4-3: Target resource requirements for the water extraction demonstrator

Parameter	Value	Comments
Mass	10–15 kg	Compact unit for integration into mid-size landers.
Volume	0.02 – 0.05 m ³	Designed to fit within standard lander payload bays.
Power Consumption	50–100 W	Power for resistive heating and cold finger operation.
Operation Duration	4–6 hours	Sufficient for a single extraction experiment.
Data Output	1–2 MB per experiment	Temperature, pressure, and water collection data.

4.2.3 Targeted Lunar Mission: ESA’s European Large Logistics Lander (EL3)

ESA’s **European Large Logistics Lander (EL3)**, for which Thales Alenia Space is Prime Contractor, is designed to deliver cargo, scientific payloads, and equipment to the lunar surface as part of upcoming lunar exploration missions. EL3 will likely play a crucial role in supporting the infrastructure for long-term lunar activities, such as the Artemis program. EL3 is expected to carry payloads in the range of 1,500–1,700 kg, providing ample capacity for a range of scientific and technological experiments. The lander will offer power sources through solar panels and possibly a small nuclear power unit for extended operations during lunar nights. EL3 is expected to target sites of scientific and strategic interest, including permanently shadowed regions at the lunar poles, where water ice is believed to be abundant.

The water extraction subsystem demonstrator is considered well-suited for integration with the EL3 mission. The subsystem’s compact size (around 10–15 kg and 0.05 m³) makes it a feasible addition to the EL3 payload manifest without significantly impacting other mission objectives. The demonstrator’s estimated power consumption of 50–100 W is within the range of what the EL3 batteries can provide during night-time operations, ensuring that power demands can be met without overloading the system.

4.2.4 Key Challenges and Mitigation Strategies

Table 4-4 reports a preliminary list of identified key challenges for the identified demonstrator. For each challenge, a possible mitigation strategy is proposed.

Table 4-4: Key challenges and preliminary mitigation strategies

Title	Challenge	Mitigation
Regolith-Ice Composition Variability	The water content in lunar regolith is highly variable and may differ between regions, affecting the efficiency of the sublimation process	Before deployment, orbital data (from missions like NASA’s Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter) will be used to select regions with a high probability of containing ice. Additionally, sensors on the lander can characterize the regolith’s composition prior to extraction, helping to optimize heating parameters
Thermal Management	The extreme temperature conditions in shadowed regions (down to -170 °C) pose a risk to the heating and condensation system	Thermal insulation around the heating unit and cold finger assembly will ensure efficient heat retention and water capture. Additionally, the system will include redundant heating elements to ensure consistent performance
Power Availability	Extended lunar nights can limit the availability of solar power, which may reduce the operational time of the extraction unit	Schedule operations during lunar daytime, or, if night-time operation is required, integrate with energy storage systems such as batteries or rely on nuclear power sources planned for EL3 or future lunar bases

5 Conclusions

5.1 Summary of Findings

The LUXWEX project has made significant progress in advancing technologies for in-situ water extraction and processing on the lunar surface, specifically targeting ice deposits in permanently shadowed regions. The key findings of the project can be summarized as follows:

- **Water Extraction Process:** The LUXWEX system effectively utilizes a sublimation technique to extract water from lunar regolith containing ice. The cold finger technology, which captures water vapor after sublimation, has shown promising efficiency in laboratory tests. This process is scalable and adaptable to different environmental conditions, making it suitable for both short-term demonstration missions and long-duration lunar surface operations.
- **Water Liquefaction:** The liquefaction module has proven capable of efficiently collecting liquid water from the water ice formed onto the cold fingers.
- **Water Purification:** The purification, including filtration and adsorption technologies, have successfully demonstrated the ability to produce water of a quality suitable for life support systems and other uses in space exploration missions.
- **Performance and Resource Optimizations:** Through iterative design improvements, the LUXWEX system has achieved notable gains in terms of mass reduction, power consumption optimization, and volume efficiency. These enhancements are critical for ensuring compatibility with the payload and operational constraints of upcoming lunar missions.
- **Reliability and Serviceability:** Laboratory testing has revealed that the system is robust, with components that have the potential to ensure reliability in harsh lunar conditions. The modular design also allows for straightforward maintenance and potential in-situ repairs, increasing the system's resilience for long-duration missions.
- **Technology Readiness Level (TRL) Progression:** Based on the performance of the individual process-specific modules and their integration into a cohesive system, LUXWEX has reached a TRL sufficient for near-term lunar demonstration missions. The technology is poised for further testing and validation in lunar analog environments, with a clear roadmap for future development.

5.2 Recommendations for Future Work

To further enhance the readiness and application of LUXWEX technologies for lunar missions, several key areas of future work and recommendations have been identified:

- **Technologies design iteration:** The next critical step for LUXWEX is an iteration of the design some of the key technologies in order to implement the lessons learnt from the laboratory test campaign. This will include:
 - Addition of excavation or drilling, as per section 2.2.1
 - Revise the heated stirring solution, as per section 2.2.1
 - Revise the solution for emptying of dry regolith, as per section 2.2.1
 - Revise design against lunar dust simulant of movable parts of WECS, as per section 2.2.1
 - Addition of the activated carbon steam regeneration system to the Water Purification System, as detailed in section 2.2.2.a
 - Evaluation of the addition of a photocatalytic reactor to the Water Purification System for methanol degradation, as detailed in section 2.2.2.b
 - Revise technological choice for pH, EC and turbidity sensors, as per section 2.2.3

- **Full System Demonstration on Lunar Surface:** The next critical step for LUXEX is a full system demonstration on the lunar surface. This can be accomplished in collaboration with upcoming lunar missions, such as ESA's European Large Logistics Lander (EL3) or NASA's Artemis program. The focus should be on demonstrating the system's ability to extract, liquefy, and purify water in the lunar environment, under operational constraints typical of long-duration missions.
- **System Optimization for Early Demonstration Missions:** For early missions with more limited payload capacity, a scaled-down version of the LUXEX system should be deployed to test individual modules (e.g., water extraction or liquefaction) in situ. This will provide valuable data on system performance in real lunar conditions, while mitigating the risks associated with deploying the full system from the outset.
- **Power and Thermal Management Enhancements:** Although the current design has demonstrated energy efficiency, further optimization of power usage is essential, particularly for long lunar nights or shadowed regions. Similarly, enhancing the thermal management system will improve system performance in the Moon's extreme temperature ranges, ensuring reliable operation across various mission profiles.
- **Integration with ISRU and Lunar Infrastructure:** As lunar exploration progresses, LUXEX technologies should be integrated with other in-situ resource utilization (ISRU) systems, such as oxygen extraction from regolith or fuel production. Establishing synergies between water extraction and broader ISRU activities will enhance mission sustainability and reduce reliance on Earth-supplied resources. In addition, ensuring compatibility with future lunar habitats and base infrastructure will be crucial for long-term mission success.
- **Automation and Remote Operation:** Given the constraints of lunar missions—such as limited human presence and the need for autonomy—LUXEX should continue to enhance its automation capabilities. The goal is to develop a system that can operate independently, with minimal need for human intervention, and be monitored or controlled remotely from mission control on Earth.
- **Long-Duration Testing in Lunar Analog Environments:** Before deploying the LUXEX system on the lunar surface, it is recommended that long-duration testing be conducted in lunar analog environments on Earth. These tests should simulate the thermal, vacuum, and dust conditions of the lunar surface, allowing for further refinements and de-risking of the system.
- **Partnerships and Mission Opportunities:** Engaging with international space agencies and commercial partners will be vital to ensure LUXEX is included in upcoming lunar missions. By leveraging the infrastructure and flight opportunities provided by these partnerships, LUXEX can progress towards full-scale deployment on the Moon.

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